

Interview Scheduleⁱ

1. What is your present role / designation?
2. How long have you occupied this role?
3. What is the value of your role within this museum?
4. Describe 2-3 examples of your engagement with (prospective) visitors of this museum.
5. Have you observed any changes in the demographics of visitors since you first started filling this role?
Please give specific examples (*if needed, prompt with gender, age, ethnic/ability minority backgrounds etc.*).
Why do you think such changes did / did not take place?
6. To what extent and in what ways do you see this museum responding to what you have just described? (*if needed prompt the interviewee with generic examples such as policies, technologies, training for staff, etc.*)
7. What are the impacts (if any) of the described museum's responses (or lack of them) on:
 - a. public engagement (or limitations to this) with this museum?
 - b. public engagement (or limitations to this) with museums in general?
 - c. how society develops? (*if needed refer to aspects of sustainable development such as quality education for all, inclusion, equality and equity, reduction of poverty and climate change, etc.*)
 - d. your role in this museum?
8. In your assessment, is this museum representing specific groups / social realities?
Give specific examples.
What are the impacts of (limited) representation?
9. Which knowledge and skills that you already have enable you to provide (prospective) visitors with an equitable and inclusive educational experience?

10. When / Why do you feel challenged with providing (prospective) visitors with an equitable and inclusive educational experience of this museum?
11. How can you tell that visitors are learning from this museum's experience?
Give specific examples.
12. If any, what sort of learning does the visitor experience (knowledge and skills)?
13. To what extent does your role facilitate such learning?
Give specific examples.
What are the assets / challenges to the above?
14. Which assets (if any) do specific social cohorts have that facilitate educational outcomes when engaging with this museum?
15. What challenges (if any) do specific social cohorts face when it comes to yielding educational outcomes when engaging with this museum?
16. Would you like to add anything else?

ⁱ Overarching research questions of the study:

- To what extent (can) the museums under study feature culturally intersectional *agoras* that (can) educate on and practise sustainable inclusivity and equality - including gender equality?

- What learning outcomes are foundational to professional development that supports museum personnel in European contexts with democratically and dialogically engaging diverse publics?